

Digital Literacy in Education: Preparing Students for the Future Workforce

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Abstract:

Overview: In today's rapidly evolving technological landscape, digital literacy has emerged as a crucial skill for preparing students for the future workforce. As industries become increasingly digitized, the ability to navigate, analyze, and utilize digital tools and platforms is no longer just an advantage but a necessity. This study explored the importance of equipping students with the necessary digital skills to thrive in a technology-driven job market.

Body of Knowledge: Digital literacy encompasses a broad range of competencies, including the ability to access and evaluate information, communicate effectively through digital mediums, and apply critical thinking to solve complex problems in a digital environment. These skills are essential for students to thrive in a world where technology drives innovation and efficiency. The integration of digital literacy into the curriculum is vital for equipping students with the competencies needed to succeed in emerging job markets, where digital competencies are highly valued by employers.

Methods: The study adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to provide a robust analysis. The study was aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how digital literacy impacts students' readiness for the workforce in 4 selected learning institutions; 2 belonging to secondary schools and 2 belonging to higher learning institutions within Lusaka district in Zambia. The sample consisted 160 respondents; Lecturers, Teachers, Student and Pupils. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically.

Results: The findings revealed that the integration of digital literacy into educational curricula is vital for ensuring that students are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to adapt to the demands of modern workplaces. In addition, the findings noted that digital literacy plays a significant role in enhancing students' employability. As more companies adopt advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, data analytics, and automation, the demand for digitally literate employees continues to rise.

Recommendation: The study calls for educators to ensure that students are well-prepared to meet the demands of the modern job market, thereby enhancing their employability and ability to navigate an increasingly digital world.

Keywords: Critical Thinking, Digital Competence, Education Technology, Information Literacy, and Technology Integration.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital literacy in education has become increasingly essential in preparing students for the modern workforce and ensuring they can navigate the digital world effectively. It encompasses a range of competencies, including the ability to find, evaluate, and use information, communicate and collaborate online, and understand digital tools and technologies. In educational settings, integrating digital literacy into the curriculum empowers students to develop critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and adaptability to technological changes (Yates et al, 2015). As employers increasingly value digital competencies such as data analysis, cyber security awareness, and the ability to use technology for problem-solving, fostering digital literacy in students is crucial for their future success. Furthermore, addressing socio-economic factors that impact students' access to digital resources and ensuring equitable opportunities for all learners is vital for creating a digitally literate and competitive workforce (Chanda & Phiri, 2024).

Education technology, often referred to as EdTech, encompasses a broad range of tools and resources designed to enhance teaching and learning. This field includes digital platforms, software applications, and hardware that facilitate educational processes and improve accessibility. Key elements of EdTech include Learning Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle and Blackboard, which help educators organize and deliver course content, track student progress, and facilitate communication (Mumbi & Nyirenda, 2024). Interactive technologies like smart boards and virtual reality (VR) provide immersive learning experiences, while educational apps and online resources offer personalized learning opportunities and immediate feedback. Zohaib et al (2024) alluded that the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education can tailor learning experiences to individual student needs, enabling adaptive learning pathways and automating administrative tasks. Furthermore, EdTech promotes remote and blended learning models, making education more accessible to diverse learner populations, including those in remote or underserved areas. However, Chanda (2024) noted that the effective implementation of education technology requires addressing challenges such as digital equity, ensuring that all students have access to necessary devices and high-speed internet, and providing adequate training for educators to leverage these tools effectively. As technology continues to evolve, its role in education is likely to expand, offering new possibilities for personalized learning, collaboration, and skill development essential for the future workforce (Zenke et al, 2017).

Digital competence refers to the essential skills and knowledge required to effectively use digital technologies and tools in various aspects of life, including personal, educational, and professional contexts (Ventayen, 2019). It encompasses a range of abilities, such as understanding digital environments, managing information, communicating through digital channels, and creating digital content. Digital competence also involves critical thinking and problem-solving skills, ensuring that individuals can navigate online spaces safely and responsibly. In education, digital competence is crucial for students as it prepares them for the demands of the modern workforce, where technological proficiency is often a prerequisite. It includes skills like basic computer operations, internet research, and the use of productivity software, as well as more advanced capabilities such as coding, data analysis, and digital project management. Wahyuddin (2017) says

that the development of digital competence is increasingly recognized as a key component of educational curricula, aiming to equip learners with the necessary tools to succeed in a digitalized world.

Information literacy is crucial in today's digital age, encompassing the ability to identify, locate, evaluate, and effectively use information. This skill set is foundational for academic success, informed decision-making, and lifelong learning. Information literacy involves understanding the different types of information sources, including scholarly articles, news media, and digital content, and assessing their credibility and relevance. It requires critical thinking to discern biases, verify facts, and synthesize information from various sources. In the educational context, fostering information literacy helps students develop research skills, enhance their analytical abilities, and navigate the vast information landscape (Ramsetty & Adams, 2020). It also supports the development of ethical practices in information use, ensuring that individuals respect intellectual property and avoid plagiarism. Overall, information literacy empowers individuals to be proficient and responsible users of information, essential for academic and professional growth.

Chanda et al (2024) stated that technology integration in education refers to the seamless incorporation of digital tools and resources into teaching and learning processes to enhance educational outcomes. This approach aims to enrich the learning experience by using technology to support, complement, and extend traditional pedagogical methods. Effective technology integration involves aligning digital tools with curriculum goals, using them to engage students, and leveraging their potential to foster critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving skills. Key components include the use of interactive whiteboards, educational apps, online resources, and digital platforms for collaboration (Javier & Dirain, 2018). For successful integration, educators need appropriate training and support, and schools must invest in reliable infrastructure and resources. Additionally, technology integration should be guided by clear objectives and assessed regularly to ensure it meets educational goals and addresses diverse learning needs. This holistic approach helps prepare students for a technologically driven world, equipping them with the skills necessary for the future workforce.

Critical thinking in digital literacy involves the ability to analyze, evaluate, and create information using digital tools and platforms effectively. It is essential for navigating the vast amount of information available online and making informed decisions. Eshet (2004) alluded that digital literacy requires individuals to question the credibility of sources, identify biases, and understand the context of information they encounter. Critical thinking skills enable users to discern between reliable and unreliable content, understand how digital content is produced and manipulated, and utilize digital tools to solve problems and create new knowledge. Furthermore, critical thinking in digital literacy includes evaluating the ethical implications of digital interactions, such as privacy concerns and digital footprint management. Developing these skills ensures that individuals can engage with digital environments responsibly and thoughtfully, ultimately enhancing their ability to contribute to and thrive in a digital society (Cheng et al, 2023).

1.2 Statement of the problem

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, the necessity for digital literacy in education has never been more critical. As technology continues to reshape the workforce, it is imperative that students are equipped with the skills to thrive in a digitally driven world. Digital literacy encompasses the ability to effectively and critically navigate, evaluate, and create information using a range of digital technologies (Zohaib et al, 2024). Despite its importance, many educational systems lag in integrating comprehensive digital literacy programs into their curricula, leading to a gap between students' current skill levels and the demands of the modern job market. Chanda et al (2024) says that this gap not only hampers students' preparedness for future careers but also limits their ability to engage fully with contemporary technological tools and platforms. The problem, therefore, lies in the insufficient emphasis on digital literacy within educational frameworks, which fails to adequately prepare students for the future workforce. Addressing this issue involves developing and implementing robust digital literacy programs that span various educational levels, ensuring students acquire the necessary skills to adapt to and excel in an increasingly digital professional environment.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess the effectiveness of current educational practices in integrating digital literacy into the curriculum and to identify gaps in students' preparedness for digital challenges in the workplace.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To determine the existing proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills in selected learning institutions within Lusaka district, Zambia.
- To investigate which digital competencies and technological skills are most valued by employers and are essential for success in emerging job markets.

1.5 Conceptual Framework

The study revolved around the integration of digital literacy into educational curricula to equip students with the essential skills required for the modern job market. Digital literacy encompasses a range of competencies, including the ability to effectively use technology, understand digital communication, and critically evaluate online information (Anft, 2020). This framework emphasized the importance of incorporating digital literacy into core subjects and extracurricular activities to ensure that students are not only proficient in using digital tools but also adept at navigating the complexities of digital environments. By fostering digital literacy, educational institutions can help students develop problem-solving skills, adaptability, and collaborative abilities, which are crucial for the future workforce. The framework also highlighted the role of educators in modeling digital skills, providing hands-on experiences with technology, and creating an environment that encourages continuous learning and digital innovation. Ultimately, the goal is to prepare students to be competitive and effective contributors in an increasingly digital and interconnected world (Alma, 2024).

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study's significance lies in its crucial role in equipping students with the essential skills needed to thrive in an increasingly technology-driven job market. As the digital landscape evolves, proficiency in digital tools and platforms has become indispensable for career success. This study

highlights how digital literacy encompasses more than just basic computer skills; it involves critical thinking, problem-solving, and the ability to navigate complex digital environments effectively. By focusing on digital literacy, educational institutions can ensure that students are not only familiar with current technologies but are also adaptable to future innovations. This preparedness enhances their employability, allowing them to meet the demands of modern employers who prioritize technological competence. Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of integrating digital literacy into curricula to bridge the gap between educational outcomes and industry needs, fostering a workforce capable of driving progress and innovation in various sectors.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to provide a robust analysis (Banda et al, 2017). This mixed-methods approach allowed for a nuanced understanding of how digital literacy influences workforce readiness and inform recommendations for educational practices aimed at enhancing students' digital competencies for future career. The study was aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how digital literacy impacts students' readiness for the workforce in 4 selected learning institutions; 2 belonging to secondary schools and 2 belonging to higher learning institutions within Lusaka district in Zambia. The sample consisted 160 respondents; 10% of the target population 1600. The population for the study was purposefully drawn from the 4 institutions. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select lecturers and teachers (20); 5 representing each institution and school while the simple random sampling procedure was used to select the students and pupils (140); 35 representing each institution and school. The data collection process involved distributing the questionnaires to the selected participants and conducting individual interviews. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The study avoided pressuring respondents to take part in the research. Alternatively, permission consents, assents were obtained from respondents involved in the research and the research topic was strategically selected to ensure that there was no harm whatsoever to the research respondents. The study also upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Proficiency of Students and Pupils in Essential Digital Skills

According to research findings, the proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills within learning institutions varies widely, influenced by factors such as access to technology, quality of digital education, and socio-economic background. The results revealed that access to technology is a critical factor that significantly influences the proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills. In today's increasingly digital world, the availability and accessibility of technological resources such as computers, tablets, smartphones, and reliable internet connectivity are fundamental to developing digital literacy (Allen & Seaman, 2017). Students and pupils who have regular access to these technologies are more likely to develop proficiency in essential digital

skills, including word processing, online research, digital communication, and the use of various educational software. This proficiency is not only crucial for their academic success but also for their ability to navigate the broader digital landscape, which is increasingly becoming a prerequisite in the workforce (Nazzal et al, 2021).

However, access to technology remains uneven, particularly in areas with socio-economic disparities. Chanda et al, (2024)'s study revealed that in many rural or underprivileged urban areas, students and pupils may lack adequate access to modern technology, thereby hindering their ability to develop essential digital skills. This digital divide creates a significant barrier to equal educational opportunities, as those without access to technology are at a disadvantage in developing the skills needed for the digital economy. Addressing this issue requires concerted efforts from governments, educational institutions, and other stakeholders to ensure that all students and pupils, regardless of their socio-economic background, have the necessary access to technology (Lăzăroiu et al, 2021). This includes not only providing physical devices but also ensuring that there is reliable internet access and relevant training for both students and educators to effectively utilize these technologies in educational settings.

Additionally, socio-economic factors play a significant role in shaping the proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills. These factors, which include income levels, parental education, access to technology, and the broader socio-economic environment, create disparities in digital literacy. Students from higher-income families are more likely to have access to personal computers, reliable internet, and other digital tools at home, which fosters early and continuous exposure to technology (Chanda et al, 2023). This early exposure often translates into greater comfort and skill in using digital tools for learning and problem-solving. In contrast, students from lower-income backgrounds may face challenges such as limited or no access to digital devices and the internet at home. These barriers can lead to a digital divide, where these students lag in developing essential digital skills compared to their peers from more affluent backgrounds. Additionally, the educational level of parents can influence how much support students receive in developing digital skills. Parents with higher levels of education are often more equipped to guide their children in using technology effectively, thereby enhancing their proficiency. The socio-economic environment of the community and school also contributes to the development of digital skills (Xu et al, 2023). Schools in wealthier areas are more likely to have well-equipped computer labs, up-to-date software, and teachers who are trained in integrating technology into the curriculum. Conversely, schools in economically disadvantaged areas may struggle with outdated equipment, limited resources, and a lack of trained personnel, further widening the gap in digital proficiency. Addressing these socio-economic disparities is crucial for ensuring that all students have the opportunity to develop the essential digital skills needed for future academic and professional success.

The findings also revealed that curriculum integration plays a pivotal role in developing and enhancing the proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills. Wang et al (2023) narrated that when digital literacy is embedded within the curriculum, students are not only exposed to technology but also learn to apply digital tools in meaningful and contextually relevant ways. This approach ensures that digital skills are not taught in isolation but are intertwined with various subjects, allowing students to see the practical applications of technology across different areas of study. For instance, incorporating digital tools in research projects, data analysis in

mathematics, or presentations in social studies helps students build a robust digital skill set that is transferable to real-world situations (Chanda et al, 2024).

Moreover, curriculum integration fosters a deeper understanding of digital literacy by encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving. As students engage with digital content across subjects, they learn to navigate, evaluate, and create digital information more effectively. This comprehensive approach prepares students to become proficient in essential digital skills, equipping them to thrive in a technology-driven world (.William & Bomm, 2024). The consistent exposure to and practice of digital skills within various curricular activities also helps to bridge the digital divide, ensuring that all students, regardless of their background, have the opportunity to develop these vital competencies. Furthermore, integrating digital skills into the curriculum supports the development of lifelong learning habits. As students encounter technology across different subjects, they become more adaptable and open to learning new tools and platforms. This adaptability is crucial in a rapidly evolving digital landscape, where the ability to learn and apply new technologies can significantly impact future career opportunities. Walker et al (2020) noted that curriculum integration is a fundamental aspect of ensuring that students and pupils achieve proficiency in essential digital skills, thereby preparing them for the demands of the modern workforce and society.

Teachers alluded that teacher proficiency plays a critical role in shaping the digital skills of students and pupils, serving as a foundation for their ability to navigate the digital world effectively. One of the teachers expressed that:

“When teachers possess a high level of digital proficiency, they are better equipped to integrate technology into their teaching practices, thereby enhancing the learning experience for their students”.

This integration not only familiarizes students with digital tools but also encourages the development of essential digital skills that are crucial for success in today’s technologically driven society. A teacher’s ability to effectively use digital tools in the classroom significantly influences students’ proficiency in essential digital skills. Teachers who are proficient in digital literacy can model appropriate use of technology, guiding students in understanding how to use these tools responsibly and effectively. This modeling is crucial, as it provides students with real-life examples of how digital skills can be applied in various contexts, from academic research to everyday problem-solving. Furthermore, teachers who are digitally proficient are more likely to create learning environments that are rich in digital resources, offering students numerous opportunities to practice and refine their skills (Mpolomoka et al, 2017).

The impact of teacher proficiency on students’ digital skills extends beyond the classroom. Teachers with a strong command of digital tools are more likely to design and assign tasks that require students to engage with technology in meaningful ways. Chanda (2024) added that this not only enhances students’ technical skills but also promotes critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. For example, a teacher proficient in using educational software may assign projects that require students to collaborate online, analyze data using digital tools, or create multimedia presentations. These activities help students develop a deeper understanding of how to use technology to achieve specific goals, thus reinforcing their digital proficiency. However, the proficiency of teachers in digital skills varies widely, which can create disparities in the digital skills of students. Warschauer & Matuchniak (2010) supported this finding by stating that in cases

where teachers lack digital proficiency, students may receive limited exposure to digital tools and resources, hindering their ability to develop essential digital skills. This gap in teacher proficiency can be particularly pronounced in regions with limited access to technology or inadequate professional development opportunities for teachers. As a result, students in these areas may struggle to keep pace with their peers in more digitally advanced environments, perpetuating a cycle of digital inequality.

Lecturers pointed out that information literacy plays a critical role as an existing proficiency of students and pupils in essential digital skills. It refers to the ability to locate, evaluate, and effectively use information, which is a key component in today's digital landscape (Thomas & Brown, 2011). In educational contexts, information literacy is essential for students and pupils to navigate vast amounts of data available through digital platforms. The proficiency in information literacy involves not only understanding how to access credible sources but also the ability to critically analyze the information they encounter online, distinguishing between reliable and unreliable content. Moreover, students who possess strong information literacy skills are better equipped to use digital tools to research, learn, and apply knowledge across various subjects (Chanda & Zohaib, 2024). These skills allow them to approach academic tasks with a more discerning eye, improving the quality of their work. In contrast, a lack of proficiency in information literacy can lead to misinformation or an overreliance on unverified sources, which can negatively impact their academic performance. Furthermore, as information literacy extends beyond academic use into everyday life, students who are proficient are more likely to make informed decisions in their personal and future professional lives, thus enhancing their digital fluency overall. In many educational systems, fostering information literacy is increasingly becoming a part of the curriculum as educators recognize its importance in shaping digitally competent students. However, gaps still exist, particularly in schools where digital resources are limited or where there is a lack of trained educators to teach these skills. Therefore, integrating information literacy into the development of essential digital skills remains a vital part of preparing students for a future where digital and information proficiencies will continue to be in high demand.

The results further noted that communication and collaboration are fundamental aspects of digital literacy that significantly influence the proficiency of students and pupils in navigating the modern digital landscape. As digital tools become increasingly embedded in educational settings, the ability to communicate effectively and collaborate with peers, teachers, and external stakeholders has emerged as a critical skill set. Students today are expected to interact through various digital platforms, including email, social media, learning management systems, and collaborative tools like Google Docs and Microsoft Teams (Gaber et al, 2020). This proficiency is not only about using these tools but also about understanding digital etiquette, cultural sensitivity, and the nuances of digital communication that differ from face-to-face interactions.

Furthermore, collaboration in digital environments requires students to work effectively in teams, often across geographic and cultural boundaries. This involves not only the technical ability to use collaborative software but also the development of interpersonal skills that foster teamwork, such as active listening, clear articulation of ideas, and the ability to provide and receive constructive feedback. The increasing emphasis on group projects and peer-to-peer learning in educational curricula reflects the growing importance of these skills (Mpolomoka et al, 2023). As students and pupils engage in collaborative tasks, they develop a sense of responsibility and accountability,

learning to manage their time, contribute meaningfully to group efforts, and resolve conflicts that may arise in a digital setting. Moreover, proficiency in communication and collaboration through digital platforms is essential for preparing students for the workforce, where remote work and virtual teams are becoming more common. Employers increasingly value candidates who can demonstrate effective digital communication and collaboration skills, making these competencies crucial for career readiness. Therefore, educators must continue to integrate opportunities for students to practice and refine these skills within the curriculum, ensuring that they are well-equipped to succeed in both academic and professional environments (Zohaib et al, 2024).

Figure1: Proficiency of Students and Pupils in Essential Digital Skills

3.2. Digital Competencies and Technological Skills Which Are Most Valued

The results revealed that digital competencies and technological skills are increasingly prioritized by employers in learning institutions as they prepare students for the demands of emerging job markets. These skills are seen as critical for success due to the rapid integration of technology across various industries. According to data collected from respondents; Digital Literacy was identified to be at 30%, Problem-Solving Using Technology at 25%, Data Analysis at 20%, Cyber security Awareness at 15%, and Adaptability to Technological Changes at 10%.

The study results noted that digital literacy has emerged as a critical component in the educational landscape, particularly as digital competencies and technological skills are increasingly valued by employers in learning institutions. As the job market continues to evolve with the rapid advancement of technology, the ability to navigate and effectively utilize digital tools is no longer a supplementary skill but a necessity for success. Employers are seeking individuals who are not only proficient in basic digital tasks but also capable of adapting to new technologies, engaging in

complex problem-solving using digital tools, and contributing to innovation within their fields (Makombo et al, 2024).

In learning institutions, there is a growing recognition that equipping students with these competencies is crucial for their future employability. The emphasis on digital literacy in education reflects the demands of the modern workforce, where digital fluency is linked to productivity, creativity, and the ability to collaborate across diverse and often global teams. Institutions that prioritize the development of digital skills are better positioned to prepare students for the challenges of the emerging job market, where roles are increasingly defined by technological expertise (Miller & Hafner, 2008).

Moreover, the integration of digital literacy into the curriculum helps bridge the gap between education and industry expectations. Employers are looking for graduates who can seamlessly transition into the workforce with the ability to use digital tools to analyze data, communicate effectively, and contribute to digital transformation initiatives within organizations. This alignment between education and employer needs ensures that students are not only academically prepared but also possess the practical skills required to thrive in a technology-driven environment. Ultimately, the focus on digital literacy within learning institutions underscores the importance of preparing students for a future where digital competencies are essential for both personal and professional success (Lave & Wenger, 2015). As the job market continues to shift towards more technology-oriented roles, the ability to demonstrate digital literacy will be a key differentiator for job seekers, making it a vital area of focus for educators and policymakers alike.

The findings also revealed that in the rapidly evolving job market, problem-solving using technology has become an indispensable digital competency highly valued by employers, particularly within learning institutions (Kim, 2019). The ability to leverage technology to address complex challenges is not just a desirable skill; it is essential for success in emerging job markets where digital transformation is redefining traditional roles. One of the lecturers pointed out that:

“Employers seek individuals who can navigate digital tools, software, and platforms to innovate, streamline processes, and provide effective solutions to problems. This proficiency enables workers to stay competitive in environments that increasingly rely on data-driven decision-making and automation”.

Moreover, in educational institutions, the emphasis on technological problem-solving skills reflects a broader recognition of their role in preparing students for future careers. As industries adapt to new technologies, the demand for employees who can efficiently use these tools to solve problems grows. Educational programs are thus integrating these competencies into curricula, ensuring that students are not only tech-savvy but also capable of applying their knowledge in real-world situations. This shift underscores the importance of digital literacy and critical thinking, as students are trained to analyze issues from multiple angles, propose viable solutions, and execute them using the latest technological advancements (.Kavi et al, 2019) Furthermore, as organizations continue to adopt new technologies, problem-solving skills using technology are becoming critical for innovation and growth. Employees who possess these skills can help companies stay ahead of competitors by identifying opportunities for improvement and implementing technology-driven solutions. This makes them valuable assets in any organization, particularly in sectors where the pace of technological change is rapid. Consequently, the cultivation of these competencies within

educational institutions not only enhances students' employability but also equips them with the tools necessary to succeed in a dynamic, technology-driven job market (Dijk, 2020).

Furthermore, data analysis has emerged as one of the most critical digital competencies valued by employers in learning institutions, particularly as the demand for data-driven decision-making grows across various sectors. The ability to collect, process, and interpret vast amounts of data is increasingly recognized as a fundamental skill that not only enhances academic and operational efficiency but also prepares students for the demands of the modern workforce. Employers prioritize data analysis skills because they enable individuals to identify trends, make informed predictions, and contribute to evidence-based decision-making processes. This competency is essential in educational settings where data is used to assess student performance, evaluate program effectiveness, and optimize resource allocation (Chanda, 2024). Moreover, data analysis is vital for success in emerging job markets that are increasingly defined by rapid technological advancements and the proliferation of big data. As industries across the globe integrate more sophisticated technologies, the ability to analyze data becomes indispensable for professionals seeking to stay competitive. Employers in various fields, including finance, healthcare, marketing, and education, are on the lookout for candidates who can leverage data to drive innovation, improve processes, and solve complex problems (Buckingham, 2007). In this context, learning institutions are under pressure to incorporate data analysis into their curricula to ensure that students are equipped with the skills necessary to thrive in a data-driven economy.

In addition to technical proficiency, the ability to analyze data fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, which are highly valued in today's job market. Students who are adept at data analysis are better positioned to approach challenges with a methodical and analytical mindset, making them valuable assets to employers (Braxton et al, 2000). This skill set also opens up opportunities for students in a wide range of careers, as the need for data-literate professionals spans multiple industries. Consequently, learning institutions must prioritize the development of data analysis competencies to align their educational offerings with the evolving needs of the labor market. Data analysis stands out as a digital competency that is not only highly valued by employers in learning institutions but also essential for success in emerging job markets. UNESCO (2018) revealed that as the world becomes increasingly data-driven, the ability to analyze and interpret data will continue to be a key determinant of professional success, making it imperative for educational institutions to integrate data analysis into their programs. By doing so, they will not only enhance their students' employability but also contribute to the broader goal of fostering a workforce that is equipped to navigate and excel in the complexities of the modern economy.

Respondents also alluded cyber security awareness has emerged as a critical digital competency and technological skill that employers highly value in learning institutions. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the risks associated with cyber threats have increased, making cyber security knowledge essential for both students and professionals (Wuyckens et al, 2021). In today's job market, where data breaches and cyber-attacks are prevalent, having a strong understanding of cyber security practices is not only a valuable asset but also a necessity for success. Employers in various industries are increasingly seeking individuals who are not only proficient in their technical roles but also possess the awareness and skills to protect sensitive information and systems from cyber threats. Learning institutions are therefore emphasizing cyber security education to equip students with the necessary knowledge to navigate the complexities of the digital world safely.

This focus on cyber security is critical because it prepares students to recognize potential threats, understand best practices for safeguarding data, and implement security measures in their future workplaces. In addition to technical skills, cyber security awareness fosters a proactive mindset, enabling individuals to anticipate and mitigate potential risks. This capability is particularly important in emerging job markets, where technology is rapidly advancing and the demand for cyber security professionals is growing. By integrating cyber security education into the curriculum, learning institutions are not only meeting the current needs of employers but also preparing students for the future workforce, where digital security will continue to be a priority (Van Laar et al, 2017).

The study findings noted that adaptability to technological changes is increasingly recognized as one of the most critical digital competencies in today's rapidly evolving job markets. Employers in learning institutions value this skill highly because the ability to quickly learn and adapt to new technologies is essential for staying competitive and relevant. As digital tools, platforms, and systems continue to advance, individuals who can seamlessly transition to using these new technologies are better equipped to contribute effectively to their organizations. This adaptability not only enhances personal productivity but also fosters innovation and continuous improvement within the workplace (Potter, 2016). In the context of education, adaptability to technological changes is crucial for both students and educators. As learning environments incorporate more digital resources, those who are proficient in adopting and integrating these tools can better support the educational process. One of the students stated that:

“Developing this competency prepares them for the dynamic nature of modern workplaces, where new technologies are regularly introduced”.

For educators, adaptability allows them to enhance their teaching methods, engage students more effectively, and stay updated with the latest educational technologies (Yang et al, 2021). Moreover, the demand for adaptability in the workforce is driven by the emergence of new job roles and industries that are heavily reliant on technology. As traditional job roles evolve or become obsolete, those who can quickly up skill or reskill using new technologies will have a significant advantage in the job market. Therefore, fostering adaptability to technological changes is not just about staying current with the latest tools; it's about cultivating a mindset of lifelong learning and resilience in the face of technological disruptions (Tewell, 2015). This makes it an indispensable skill for success in emerging job markets.

Figure2: Digital Competencies and Technological Skills Which Are Most Valued

4. CONCLUSION

Digital literacy is increasingly vital in preparing students and pupils for the future workforce. As technology rapidly evolves, the ability to navigate and utilize digital tools becomes crucial for success in various career fields. This competence encompasses a range of skills, including proficiency in essential digital skills, problem-solving with technology, data analysis, and cybersecurity awareness. Schools and educational institutions must integrate digital literacy into their curricula to ensure that students are not only familiar with current technologies but also adaptable to future advancements. By fostering these skills, educators can equip students to meet the demands of the modern job market, where technological adaptability and digital proficiency are highly valued. This preparation not only enhances students' employability but also empowers them to contribute effectively in a digital-driven economy. Thus, prioritizing digital literacy in education is essential for bridging the gap between academic learning and professional requirements, ultimately shaping a workforce that is both capable and competitive.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. Integrate Digital Literacy Across the Curriculum:

- Schools should embed digital literacy skills across all subject areas rather than confining them to standalone courses. This approach ensures that students are continually practicing and applying digital skills in various contexts.

2. Professional Development for Educators:

- There is need for educators need ongoing professional development that focuses on the latest digital tools, pedagogical strategies for digital education, and ways to assess digital competencies. Training should include hands-on experience with new technologies, best practices for integrating digital tools into lessons, and techniques for fostering digital citizenship among students.

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